

Base-catalysed cyclocondensation of α,α' -bis(arylmethylene)cyclohexanones with thiourea : Formation of *E*-8-(arylmethylene)-4-aryl-1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8-octahydrobenzo[*d*]pyrimidine-2-thiones

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Abstract : Base-catalysed cyclocondensation of α,α' -bis(arylmethylene)cyclohexanones with thiourea has been found to generate *E*-8-(arylmethylene)-4-aryl-1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8-octahydrobenzo[*d*]pyrimidine-2-thiones in high yield, the structures of which have been established from their spectral data. However, corresponding cyclopentanones were found to be unreactive under similar reaction condition.

Keywords : α,α' -Bis(arylmethylene)cycloalkanones, thiourea, *E*-8-(arylmethylene)-4-aryl-1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8-octahydrobenzo[*d*]pyrimidine-2-thiones.

Introduction

As a part of our continued interest in synthesis of new fused heterocycles having potential biological activities^{1,2}, we carried out a synthesis of (4*S**,5*S**)-diphenyl-1,3,4,5-tetrahydro-2*H*-[1]benzopyrano-[4,3-*d*]pyrimidine-2-thiones² (**1**) by base-catalysed cyclocondensation of *E*-3-benzylidene flavanones (**2**) with thiourea. *E*-3-Benzylidene flavanones possess a part similar to chalcones (**3**), and Al-Hajjar *et al.* assigned the correct structure **4** to the cyclocondensation product of chalcones with thiourea³. However, their assigned structure **5** to the monoacetyl derivative of these compounds, formed on treatment with acetic anhydride, was not correct. We were the first to assign the correct structure **6** to the monoacetyl derivative of **4** from detailed NMR spectral studies². This enabled us to assign the structure **7** to the monoacetyl derivative of **1**².

α,α' -Bis(arylmethylene)cycloalkanones (**8** and **9**), readily obtainable from cycloalkanones and aromatic aldehydes, were recently utilized by us for investigating their reaction with indole⁴. In this paper we report the results of base-catalysed condensation of α,α' -bis(arylmethylene)cycloalkanones (**8** and **9**) as well as 3-benzylidenechromanones (**10**) with thiourea.

Results and discussion

When each of the symmetrical α,α' -bis(arylmethylene)-

cyclohexanones **8a-d** (1 mol) was treated with thiourea (1 or 2 mol) in dry methanol in the presence of sodium methoxide under refluxing condition, a single product was obtained in good yield (Scheme 1, Table 1). Analytical and spectral data of the products definitely showed that only 1 : 1 cyclocondensation products, *E*-8-(arylmethylene)-4-aryl-1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8-octahydrobenzo[*d*]pyrimidine-2-thiones (**10a-d**) were formed. In case of the unsymmetrical starting material **8e**, the reaction was not at all regioselective and a mixture of two isomeric products **10e'** and **10e''** in the approximate ratio 3 : 2 resulted. These two isomeric compounds could not be separated by exhaustive column chromatography over silica gel as well as neutral alumina. Our attempts to synthesise the lower homologue of **10** by starting from α,α' -bis(arylmethylene)cyclopentanones **9a-c** and use of the aforesaid reaction condition or its slight modification (vide Experimental), however, did not meet with success. So far, we have not got any rationale for this observation.

Acetylation of three compounds of the series **10** (**10b-d**) was studied and each of them gave only one monoacetyl derivative (**11a-c**, respectively) having acetylation site at the amino nitrogen, analogous to **1** and **4**.

Reaction of benzylidenechromanone (**12**) with thiourea done in this connection gave **13** in high yield and its acetylation produced the monoacetyl compound **14**.

Scheme 1

Table 1. Results of cyclocondensation of α,α' -bis(arylmethylene)cyclohexanones with thiourea

Entry	Starting bis(arylmethylene)-cyclohexanone	Reaction time (h)	Isolated product	Yield (%)	m.p. (°C)
1	8a	2.5	10a	60	186–188
2	8b	3	10b	55	176–178
3	8c	2	10c	70	230–232
4	8d	3	10d	75	221–222
5	8e	3	10e' and 10e'' (Inseparable)	50	–

†The products were characterised from their spectral data.

Experimental

Melting points were recorded on a Kofler block and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded in KBr on a Perkin-Elmer 397 spectrophotometer. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded in CDCl_3 on two Bruker AV-300 (300 MHz) spectrometers using TMS as internal standard. High Resolution Mass Spectra were recorded on Micro Mass QTOF spectrometer.

Analytical samples were routinely dried *in vacuo* at room temperature. Column chromatography was performed with silica gel (100–200 mesh) and TLC with silica gel G of SRL Pvt. Ltd. Petroleum ether had the boiling range 60–80 °C.

α, α' -Bis(arylmethylene)cyclohexanones, were easily prepared⁵ by condensation of available cycloalkanones and aromatic aldehydes in aqueous ethanolic sodium hydroxide and they were properly characterised⁴. The melting points of the α, α' -bis(arylmethylene)cycloalkanones were as follows : **8a**, 155 °C; **8b**, 213 °C; **8c**, 138 °C; **8d**, 162–163 °C; **8e**, 92–94 °C, **9a**, 190 °C; **9b**, 215 °C; **9c**, 229–230 °C.

General procedure for reaction of α, α' -bis(arylmethylene)cycloalkanones with thiourea :

A mixture of thiourea (1 or 2 mmol) and sodium methoxide [prepared from sodium (230 mg) and dry metha-

nol (10 ml)] in dry methanol (60 ml) was stirred for 15 min. To this mixture α, α' -bis(arylmethylene)cycloalkanones (1 mmol) was added. The resulting mixture was refluxed in boiling water bath for 2–3 h and then cooled. It was then poured onto ice and the solid thus obtained was filtered off, washed with water until it was alkali free. The crude product was extracted with chloroform and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The concentrate of the chloroform extract was chromatographed over silica gel using petroleum ether-ethyl acetate (8 : 2) as eluent to obtain the pure product.

10a : IR : ν_{max} (KBr) : 3180 (N-H), 1668, 1569, 1488, 1188 (C=S) cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) : δ 1.77–1.99 (2H, m, H₂-6), 2.54–2.71 (4H, m, H₂-5 and H₂-7), 5.01 (1H, s, H-4), 5.12 (1H, s, N-H), 5.34 (1H, s, N-H), 6.67–7.80 (11H, m, Ar-H and H-11); HRMS (ESI) Calcd. for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_2\text{S}$ (M+Na)⁺ : 355.1245; found 355.1248.

10b : IR : ν_{max} (KBr) : 3180 (N-H), 1604, 1568, 1508, 1188 (C=S) cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) : δ 1.96–1.98 (2H, m, H₂-6), 2.56–2.70 (4H, m, H₂-5 and H₂-7), 3.80 (3H, s, OCH₃), 3.82 (3H, s, OCH₃), 4.94 (1H, s, H-4), 5.06 (1H, s, N-H), 5.27 (1H, s, N-H), 6.81–7.61 (9H, m, Ar-H and H-11).

10c : IR : ν_{\max} (KBr) : 3267–3176 (N–H), 1585, 1573, 1488, 1191 (C=S) cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) : δ 1.80–2.02 (2H, m, H_2 -6), 2.41–2.70 (4H, m, H_2 -5 and H_2 -7), 4.90 (1H, s, H-4), 6.52 (1H, s, H-11), 7.15 (1H, s, N–H), 7.18–7.37 (8H, m, Ar-H), 7.68 (1H, s, N–H); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , 75 MHz) : δ 22.24 (C-6), 25.99 (C-5), 26.64 (C-7), 60.39 (C-4), 113.47 (C-9), 121.08 (C-11), 126.73 (C-10), 128.55 (C-9), 128.59 (two carbons), 129.35 (two carbons), 130.24 (two carbons), 130.54 (two carbons), 133.13 (one carbon), 134.64 (one carbon), 134.72 (one carbon), 139.65 (one carbon), 174.22 (C=S).

10d : IR : ν_{\max} (KBr) : 3244–3196 (N–H), 1550, 1489, 1190 (C=S) cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) : δ 1.84–1.99 (2H, m, H_2 -6), 2.36 (6H, s, CH_3), 2.48–2.74 (4H, m, H_2 -5 and H_2 -7), 4.92 (1H, s, H-4), 5.07 (1H, s, N–H), 5.29 (1H, s, N–H), 6.56 (1H, s, H-11), 7.12–7.80 (8H, m, Ar-H); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , 75 MHz) : δ 21.18 (C-6), 21.23 (C-5), 22.36 (C-7), 26.05 (*p*- CH_3), 26.73 (*p'- CH_3), 60.85 (C-4), 113.43 (C-9), 121.76 (C-11), 126.55 (C-10), 127.22 (two carbons), 129.02 (two carbons), 129.16 (C-8), 129.25 (two carbons), 129.75 (two carbons), 133.41 (one carbon), 137.06 (one carbon), 138.31 (one carbon), 138.58 (one carbon), 174.00 (C=S).*

13 : Yield : 62%, m.p. 218–220 °C; IR : ν_{\max} (KBr) : 3197 (N–H), 1212 (C=S) cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) : δ 3.65 (2H, s, H_2 -5), 4.10 (1H, br. s, N–H), 4.95 (1H, s, H-4), 6.83 (1H, t, H-9), 6.95 (1H, br. d, H-7), 7.30–7.49 (2H, m, H-8 and 10), 7.27 (5H, br. s, C_6H_5), 11.84 (1H, br. s, N–H).

General procedure for acetylation of 10b-d and 13 : Each of the compounds **10b-d** and **13** (0.2 mmol) was heated with acetic anhydride (2 ml) on a boiling water bath for 1 h. After cooling it was poured into crushed ice and extracted with chloroform (3×10 ml). The chloroform layer was then washed with water (3×20 ml) and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The residue obtained by column chromatography of the crude material over silica gel furnished pure product.

11a : Yield : 85%, m.p. 152 °C; IR : ν_{\max} (KBr) : 3210 (N–H), 1664 (NHCOCH_3), 1509, 1202 (C=S) cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) : δ 1.96–1.98 (2H, m, H_2 -6), 2.56–2.70 (4H, m, H_2 -5 and H_2 -7), 2.72 (3H, s, COCH_3), 3.76 (3H, s, OCH_3), 3.83 (3H, s, OCH_3), 5.91 (1H, s, H-4), 6.47 (1H, s, H-11), 6.89–7.20 (8H, m, Ar-H), 7.90 (1H, br. s, N–H).

11b : Yield : 90%, m.p. 186–188 °C; IR : ν_{\max} (KBr) : 3203 (N–H), 1660 (NHCOCH_3), 1508, 1491, 1201 (C=S) cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) : δ 2.28–2.29 (2H, m, H_2 -6), 2.52–2.78 (4H, m, H_2 -5 and H_2 -7), 2.78 (3H, s, COCH_3), 5.96 (1H, s, H-4), 6.55 (1H, s, H-11), 7.20–7.36 (8H, m, Ar-H), 8.40 (1H, br. s, N–H); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , 75 MHz) : δ 22.25 (C-6), 26.57 (C-5), 27.10 (C-7), 27.53 (COCH_3), 58.13 (C-4), 121.26 (C-9), 121.55 (C-11), 128.62 (two carbons), 128.75 (two carbons), 128.92 (C-10), 129.14 (two carbons), 129.77 (C-8), 130.52 (two carbons), 133.27 (one carbon), 134.43 (two carbons), 136.29 (one carbon), 173.61 (C=S), 177.66 (C=O).

11c : Yield : 92%, m.p. 190 °C; IR : ν_{\max} (KBr) : 3221 (N–H), 1666 (NHCOCH_3), 1505, 1196 (C=S) cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) : δ 2.28–2.30 (2H, m, H_2 -6), 2.38 (6H, s, CH_3), 2.48–2.56 (4H, m, H_2 -5 and H_2 -7), 2.80 (3H, s, COCH_3), 5.98 (1H, s, H-4), 6.57 (1H, s, H-11), 7.10–7.29 (8H, m, Ar-H), 8.45 (1H, br. s, N–H).

14 : Yield : 80%, m.p. 172–174 °C; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) : δ 2.28 (3H, s, COCH_3), 3.83 (2H, s, H_2 -5), 5.09 (1H, s, H-4), 6.91–7.79 (9H, m, Ar-H), 11.89 (1H, br. s, N–H).

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